

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Disease Y_Detection of new infectious agent causing disease in Wildlife

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Detection of new infectious agent causing disease (Disease Y) in wildlife
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of new, disease-causing pathogens in wildlife
3	Target species and group	All wildlife
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country
6	Age group	All
7	Sampling point and strategy	Found dead by the public, hunters, farmers and others, road killed, wildlife centres, veterinary practices
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited
9	Sampling matrix	Carcasses
10	Type of disease indicators	Dead animals
11	Sampling unit	Individual animal
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	No risk factors
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Following exclusion of known pathogens, additional diagnostic investigations using metagenomics, whole genome sequencing, etc.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable

15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Not applicable
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	All other pathogens of wildlife that cause severe morbidity and mortality
18	References	Not applicable
19	Additional comments	Note: It is important to assure a timely exchange and investigations of similar cases in other animal species and humans